

Next generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials

TEA and LCA of the new AEMWE Technology

(D 6.3)

June 30, 2023 (M42)

DOI number 10.5281/zenodo.8289584

www.newely.eu

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking (now Clean Hydrogen Partnership) under Grant Agreement No **875118**. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program, Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research

Co-funded by
the European Union

Technical References

Version:	01	Date: 30.06.23	
Project Title:	Next Generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials		
Acronym:	NEWELY	Contract N°:	875118
Topic:	FCH-02-4-2019	Project Coordinator:	DLR, Germany
Document Classification: ¹	PU		
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Distribution:	All NEWELY Partners		

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Part 1: Techno-Economic Assessment (TEA)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AWE	Alkaline Water Electrolyser
PEMWE	Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyser
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolyser Cell
AEMWE	Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyser
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
LCOE	Levelised Cost of Electricity
LCOH	Levelised Cost of Hydrogen
BoP	Balance of Plant
PGM	Platinum Group Metals

Summary

This report presents the techno-economic assessment conducted for the green hydrogen production from AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE technologies.

As a starting point for the economic estimation, a suitable location is chosen to set up an electrolysis-based hydrogen production plant. The availability of wind and solar irradiation significantly affects the cost of electricity for renewable electricity generation, which further leads to variations in the cost of hydrogen. Germany, with its thriving renewable market and policies promoting green hydrogen, is an ideal country for hydrogen production within the EU. Accounting for all this, the port city of Hamburg in northern Germany is the place where the green hydrogen value chain could become cost effective. The port could act as a hub for hydrogen export or the hydrogen can be sold to nearby chemical industries which require hydrogen as feedstock.

Two operation modes, Dynamic and steady-state are evaluated, and the sizing of renewable energy sources is done accordingly. For a medium-scale hydrogen production capacity of 4000 kg/hr at a delivery pressure of 30 bar, the estimated installed electrolyzer power for AWE, PEMWE, and AEMWE electrolyzers is found to be 214 MW, 225 MW, and 221 MW, respectively. Based on the wind and solar weather data at the location the input for capacity factor and the cost of the electricity are calculated. These values are given as below,

Dynamic Operation : LCOE = 43 €/MWh; Capacity factor = 75%

Steady State Operation: LCOE = 65.5 €/MWh; Capacity factor = 90%

Using those electricity costs as input for the H₂ cost calculation, the LCOH for AEMWE based on the data and operational targets from the NEWELY Project is benchmarked against the state-of-the-art AWE and PEMWE. The LCOH results for both cases and all the electrolyser technologies are given in the figure below,

Figure 1. LCOH costs for evaluated cases and technologies

Despite AWE's economic advantage in terms of LCOH in both scenarios due to its lower power consumption and lower CAPEX, AEMWE, resulting only 6-7 % more expensive than AWE (based

on the mode of the operation) could be a more suitable technology once commercially mature due to its non-corrosive nature of operation and rapid response time. Furthermore, the study shows that LCOH from AEMWE may be 7-13% lower than from PEM (based on the mode of the operation), due to the use of less critical and cheaper materials.

A sensitivity analysis was conducted for the AEMWE system using a 1 MW stack which covered a range of values for various parameters. The study found that the electricity cost, CAPEX of the system and specific energy consumption, are in the order of impact, the most significant factors impacting the final LCOH. Improvements in these areas could significantly reduce the cost of hydrogen produced using AEMWE.

However, it is important to consider that these cost estimates are based on the assumption that all technical targets, such as power consumption, stack lifetime, and delivery pressure, are met in the development of AEMWE.

1 Introduction

Climate change unquestionably poses one of the most significant challenges we will confront in the upcoming decades. Scientific consensus solidly confirms that carbon dioxide (CO₂), a greenhouse gas, plays a pivotal role in driving climate change and the subsequent increase in global temperatures. To tackle this pressing issue, the international community has joined forces through the Paris Agreement, committing to curbing their greenhouse gas emissions by 2050. This collective endeavor strives to foster a society that is as climate-neutral as feasible, with the goal of constraining the temperature rise well below the two-degree threshold.²

To achieve a meaningful reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, extensive transformations are required across multiple sectors such as power generation, transportation, building heating, and agriculture. A key aspect of this transition is the shift towards renewable electricity or electricity-based energy carriers in these sectors. This shift will significantly increase the demand for renewable energy sources like wind and solar power, playing a critical role in meeting this demand. However, the intermittent nature of their energy generation and the limited capacity for electric storage currently pose significant challenges to their smooth implementation.

In this context, flexible chemical energy storage in the form of hydrogen can emerge as a crucial element in the future. Hydrogen, known for its versatility and clean combustion, offers numerous applications including transportation, power generation, and industrial use. By addressing the intermittent nature and storage limitations of renewable energy sources, hydrogen can become a central pillar in enabling a sustainable and low-carbon future.³

Figure 2 shows the wide array of pathways on how hydrogen can help decarbonise the economies.

Figure 2. Decarbonisation pathways using Hydrogen⁴

Currently, the predominant method for hydrogen production involves reforming hydrocarbons like methane, lignite, and oils. Although these processes generate large amounts of hydrogen at relatively low costs, they also result in substantial carbon dioxide emissions, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions. Recognizing this challenge, there is an increasing focus on

² UNFCC, The Paris Agreement, Paris Climate Change Conference, (2015)

³ Hydrogen Council, How hydrogen empowers the energy transition, (2017)

⁴ <https://blog.innovation4e.de/en/2022/03/11/sustainability-of-power-to-h2-and-power-to-liquid/>

developing sustainable alternatives for hydrogen production, particularly through the electrolysis of water using renewable electricity. This approach holds great potential in significantly reducing the overall life cycle emissions associated with hydrogen production on a global scale. By avoiding the use of fossil resources and the associated carbon emissions, this method offers a more environmentally friendly pathway for meeting the demand for hydrogen.⁵

Several countries have already introduced national hydrogen roadmaps and established targets to facilitate the adoption of electrolysis technologies for the production of green hydrogen. As an example, the European Union has outlined its objective of deploying 6 GW of electrolysis capacity by 2024, with plans to escalate it to 40 GW by 2030⁶. These ambitious targets demonstrate the commitment to achieving the goals of the Paris Climate Agreement and transitioning towards a sustainable future.

Currently, there are various water electrolysis technologies already available or in development. The cost of renewable electricity plays a significant role in determining the overall cost of hydrogen production, but the capital cost of the chosen electrolyzer system also affects the final hydrogen cost. Here are some advantages and disadvantages of the current technologies:

- Alkaline Water Electrolyser (AWE), is a well-established technology with a long history of use. The AWE electrolyser is already available in MW range of stack sizes. However, it has lower efficiency than other electrolysis technologies and requires high pH levels, which can lead to corrosion and reduced lifespan of the system. Also reported are the crossover of gases in the electrolyser system⁷.
- The Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyser (PEMWE), on the other hand, comes with higher performance and operates at higher current densities. The compact nature of the system and rapid response rate are highly favoured by the industry. The electrolyser can also be operated at higher pressure. However, PEMWE uses various expensive and scarce PGM in its components. This makes it necessary to bring in an advanced system with lower dependency on these materials. Currently, various manufacturers have announced their capabilities to produce PEMWE at the MW scale^{8,9}.
- Solid Oxide Electrolyser Cell (SOEC) electrolysis is a high-temperature electrolysis process that uses a solid oxide ceramic material as the electrolyte. The high operating temperature (typically between 700-1000°C) allows for a higher electrolysis efficiency than traditional low-temperature electrolysis. One of the key benefits of SOEC electrolysis is its high efficiency, which can lead to lower costs for hydrogen production. SOECs can also operate in reverse mode as a fuel cell, which allows for the production of electricity from hydrogen. This can be useful for energy storage or as a power source for electric vehicles. However, SOEC technology still faces challenges such as high manufacturing costs, long-term durability, and limited operational stability, which need to be addressed before it can be fully commercialised¹⁰. Due to its low maturity and high CAPEX this electrolyser technology is not considered in the following study.

⁵ IEA, The Future of Hydrogen – Seizing Today's Opportunities, (2019)

⁶ Hydrogen Europe, Clean Hydrogen Monitor, (2020)

⁷ Pozio, Alfonso & Bozza, Francesco & Nigliaccio, Giuseppe & Platter, Marzio & Monteleone, Giulia. Development perspectives on low-temperature electrolysis (2021).

⁸ <https://itm-power.com/news/two-100-mw-electrolyser-contracts-signed>

⁹ <https://www.plugpower.com/learn-more-about-plugs-electrolyzer-products/>

¹⁰ IRENA, Green Hydrogen Cost Reduction: Scaling up Electrolysers to Meet the 1.5°C Climate Goal, International Renewable Energy Agency, (2020)

- One of the emerging technologies is the Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyser (AEMWE), which can bridge the gap of the two previously discussed low temperature electrolyser technologies. The ability of the system to operate at higher current densities than traditional AWE and the use of membrane technology without the expensive materials like in PEMWE makes it a non-corrosive and low-cost alternative¹¹.

Apart from the technological differences, it becomes very important to compare these processes for their economic viabilities. This report therefore focuses on the benchmarking of the large scale AEMWE systems against the state of the art AWE and PEMWE systems. The SOEC systems are not included in the comparison due to their low maturity and the technology being still not commercialised yet.

¹¹ Immanuel Vincent, Dmitri Bessarabov, Low cost hydrogen production by anion exchange membrane electrolysis: A review, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, (2018)

2 Goal and Scope of the study

The goal of this study is to evaluate the potential cost of hydrogen using the AEM electrolysis stack being developed in the project NEWELY. In the previous deliverables of the NEWELY project, the AEM stack CAPEX and the corresponding Balance of Plant for scaled up capacities was evaluated. The system cost given in the same would be further used in the study as an input for hydrogen cost estimation.

This study also aims to benchmark the cost of hydrogen with the AEM system against other low temperature water electrolysis technologies like PEMWE and AWE. Finally, a sensitivity analysis to find the parameter mostly influencing the final H₂ cost is also provided in this report.

To assess the cost of hydrogen, parameters like hydrogen production capacities, location, delivery specification, annual operational hours, mode of operation etc. are defined in this chapter.

Figure 3 shows the basic schematic of a green hydrogen production and its application.

Figure 3. Schematic of Green Hydrogen value chain¹²

In this study, the cost of Hydrogen will include only the electricity generation and electrolyser operation. Storage, distribution and final use of hydrogen are not considered.

It is assumed that the three electrolyser technologies are directly connected to the renewable electricity generators, in this case wind and solar panels. Hydrogen is assumed to be delivered from the electrolyser at 30 bar pressure. Oxygen is not valorised in this study.

The product composition can be found in the Table 1 below,

¹² <https://www.alfalaval.com/industries/energy-and-utilities/sustainable-solutions/clean-energy/green-hydrogen/>

Table 1. Hydrogen gas production specification^{13,14}

Parameter	Unit	Value
Delivery Pressure	Barg	30
Hydrogen (H ₂) Purity	mol %	99.99
Oxygen (O ₂) Content	ppm	5
Water (H ₂ O) Content	ppm	5

2.1 Potential Location

A potential location for hydrogen production coupled with renewable electricity source is the one with ample amount of wind and solar energy and with already existing hydrogen consumers around the plant. The availability of wind and solar irradiation significantly affects the cost of electricity produced from these installations. This further leads to variation in the hydrogen cost depending on the electricity cost. Furthermore, with hydrogen being delivered directly at the site the associated costs of logistics can be eliminated.

Figure 4. Solar and Wind based electricity production potential of Germany (Solar to the Left and Wind to the Right)

¹³ ISPT, Gigawatt Green Hydrogen Plant, (2020)

¹⁴ U.S. Department of Energy, Hydrogen Fuel Quality Specification for Polymer Electrolyte Fuel Cells in Road Vehicles,(2016)

Considering the thriving renewable market in Germany, we choose this as our country of hydrogen production within the EU. The German policy makers are also promoting a renewables based green hydrogen economy via numerous grant and subsidies¹⁵ in order to incentivize the production of renewable electricity and renewable hydrogen.

The potential of electricity production from solar and wind across Germany is shown in Figure 4 above. The southernmost states have the highest solar radiation availability whereas based on the wind speed the north and middle Germany seem to be more feasible sites. Overall, wind farms have higher availability throughout the year when compared to solar PV and therefore, more emphasis is given in the production site located in the north of Germany.

Another aspect to consider is also the uptake or consumer of the produced hydrogen. The port city of Hamburg in north of Germany seems an ideal location for a renewable hydrogen project. With a number of projects already in pipeline, the city benefits with a major overhaul as key hydrogen hub in Germany¹⁶. The produced hydrogen can either be supplied to number of chemical plants in the city's vicinity or further used into mobility¹⁷. To further strengthen the case, the city also has plenty of onshore and offshore wind all around the year. Coupled with solar PV ample amount of renewable electricity shall be available for the electrolyser plant.

2.2 Production Capacities

Hydrogen production has mostly been dominated by the steam methane reforming (SMR) process, which uses natural gas as a feedstock. Almost 50% of hydrogen production today is based on traditional SMR¹⁸. SMR solutions coupled with carbon capture and sequestration technologies can lower the overall carbon emissions of hydrogen. SMR plant capacities can reach up to 200,000 Nm³/hr of hydrogen production. However, for the current estimation, a medium-scale capacity such as 45,000 Nm³/hr of hydrogen production has been selected, which is equivalent to approximately 4,000 kg/hr¹⁹. This is also more or less in line with the scale of the electrolyser plants currently under construction.

In fact, the electrolyser plant capacity has been steadily increasing in Germany over the past year. Siemens and German utility company SWW currently operate the largest electrolyser plant in the German state of Bavaria with the capacity of 8.75 MW (~160 kg/hr of H₂ at 55 kWh/kg H₂). Air Liquide plans to start operation of its 30 MW (~550 kg/hr of H₂) electrolyser plant located in Oberhausen by the end of 2023²⁰. With projects like Elygator and Normand'Hy, Air Liquide is already developing electrolyser projects of 200 MW power rating^{21,22}.

¹⁵ *The German Hydrogen Strategy*. Watson Farley and Williams. (2021). Retrieved March 8, 2022

¹⁶ Hamburg Green Hydrogen Hub, HGHH

¹⁷ GTAI, Chemical Parks in Germany, (2017)

¹⁸ Ibrahim Dincer, Canan Acar, Review and evaluation of hydrogen production methods for better sustainability, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, (2015)

¹⁹ Air Liquide Engineering and Construction, *Technology Handbook*, (2021)

²⁰ Press Release, Air Liquide, (2021)

²¹ Press Release, Air Liquide, (2021)

²² Press Release, Air Liquide, (2022)

2.3 Mode of Operation

Electrolysers can operate in dynamic or steady state mode, depending on the application and system requirements.

In dynamic mode, the electrolyser directly relies on the electricity produced by solar PV and wind installation. As the electricity production depends on the weather condition, if there are any fluctuations in the wind speed or solar irradiation this also leads to variations in the hydrogen output from the electrolyser. The total hours of annual operation in these modes are therefore not always the highest. If higher plant availability is required, the renewable power installations need to be oversized in order to get more renewable electricity leading to higher cost of the resulting power. Thus the dynamic mode of operation is driven by an optimization between the cost of the electricity and annual availability. The annual operational hours in this case would be determined based on weather data in the sections below.

In steady state mode, the electrolyser operates at a constant power input and hydrogen production rate, making it suitable for applications that require a constant supply of hydrogen. Due to this nature of operation the renewables installations are often highly oversized and configured in a way that a constant supply of electricity is always available. This results in higher capital cost for electricity generation and subsequently higher cost of electricity. These costs further reflect in the hydrogen costs, making it more expensive than the dynamic operation. Like most of the chemical plants, the targeted annual operation time under static mode is 90% i.e. the plant runs for 7884 hours annually²³.

2.4 Renewable Electricity Generation

Renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, have become increasingly popular due to their environmental benefits and decreasing costs. This section will examine the current state of solar and wind energy technologies and their costs

Solar energy is one of the most widely used renewable energy sources, with photovoltaic (PV) panels being the most common method for harnessing it. The efficiency of PV panels has been steadily improving, with the latest commercial panels having an efficiency of over 20%²⁴. Additionally, the cost of solar PV has decreased significantly over the years, with the average cost of solar PV systems falling by over 80% since 2010²⁵.

Wind energy is another widely used renewable energy source, with wind turbines being the most common method for harnessing it. The efficiency of wind turbines has also been steadily improving and the number of installations both onshore and offshore are also rising steadily²⁶. Therefore, the cost of onshore wind energy has decreased significantly over the years, with the average cost falling by almost 40% since 2010²⁷.

²³ Calculating the Capacity of Chemical Plants, AIChE, (2014)

²⁴ Photovoltaics Report, Fraunhofer ISE, (2023)

²⁵ Solar PV Global Supply Chains, IEA, (2022)

²⁶ Renewables 2020, IEA, (2020)

²⁷ Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2020, IRENA, (2020)

The total installed cost of these technologies is given in Figure 5 below. As per the available data in the year 2020, total installed costs for solar were estimated to be ~800 €/kW. Whereas, the cost of the wind installations were 50% more than that of Solar PV at ~1250 €/kW. These costs will be then further used to estimate the cost of electricity at the production site located in Hamburg, Germany

Figure 5. Total Installed Costs of Solar PV and Onshore Wind²⁷

2.5 Operational Scenarios

Based on the various points discussed in the above section and on the analysis done for the LCOE and the optimised capacity factor (Appendix A), two operational scenarios are envisioned for the electrolysis plant with a capacity of ~ 4000 kg/hr of hydrogen production operating in the north of Germany.

The first scenario is the operation in dynamic mode which is driven by the lowest cost of electricity and lowest capacity factor. Meanwhile the second case is the steady state operation driven by the availability of a minimum of 90%. Here the resulting electricity cost will be significantly higher than that in the first scenario. The assumptions for the two scenarios are summarised in the Table 2 below,

Table 2. Operational Scenarios for electrolyser plant

Parameter	Unit	Dynamic	Static
Location		Hamburg, Germany	
Hydrogen Production	Kg/hr	4000	
Capacity Factor	%	75	90

LCOE	€/MWh	37	65,5
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2.6 Methodology for LCOE

The Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is the holistic approach to estimate the cost of electricity in €/MWh. It is also known as the total lifetime cost as the period of analysis is over the total lifetime of the plant. By definition it is the total cost of constructing and operating such a plant dividing by the total electricity produced over the plant life²⁸.

The simplified equation used in this estimation is given by the equation as below,

$$LCOE (\text{€/MWh}) = \frac{I_o + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{M_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}} \quad \dots(1)$$

Where,

I_o is the total capital investment for the plant

M_t is the operating cost of renewable installation in the year t , here we assume these cost to be ~ 3% of the total capital investment²⁷

E_t is the total electricity produced in the year t . When coupled with an electrolyser we consider the electricity actually consumed by it.

r is the discount rate to estimate the net present value of all the future cash flow. A discount rate of 7% is assumed, similar to the values suggested by the International Energy Agency (IEA)²⁹

t is the total lifetime of the project, assumed to be 25 years³⁰

Thus based on all the above mentioned parameters and equation, the levelised cost of electricity can be estimated.

2.7 Renewables oversizing and Capacity factor:

The total number of electrolyser operation hours is also known as capacity factor. It is a percentage of the total time per year that electrolyser operates over the total time it can operate, given by the equation below,

$$Capacity\ factor\ (\%) = \frac{Hours\ of\ operation\ per\ year}{8760} \times 100 \quad \dots(2)$$

²⁸ UK Electricity Generation Costs: Mott MacDonald update, Department of Energy and Climate Change, (2010)

²⁹ Projected Costs of Generating Electricity, IEA, (2020)

³⁰ Global Energy and Climate Model, IEA, (2022)

To better understand the correlation between the capacity factor, LCOE and oversizing of the renewable with respect to electrolyse, weather data for a week in March for Hamburg is analysed. Using this data the total hours of electricity used by the electrolyser can be estimated. Thus, further calculating the LCOE and capacity factor for the respective configuration. Given in Figure 6, on the left are the hours of electricity generation by a 1 MW of wind installation which is coupled to a 1 MW electrolyser. The plot shows exactly how much electricity is being produced by the wind installation and what proportion of it is being used by the electrolyser. In this case the electrolyser is able to consume all electricity produced, however it can easily be seen that the full 1 MW electrolyser installation is never reached by this wind installation configuration.

Figure 6. Electrolyser operation hours for 1 MW electrolyser connected to 1 MW Wind plant on left and a 2 MW oversized Wind plant on right

(Area in orange: Electricity Consumption, Area in blue: Electricity Production)

On the right the oversized wind installation with twice the capacity than that of the electrolyser is shown. Here it can be noticed how the oversizing increases the total electricity available for the electrolysis process thus increasing the overall capacity factor of the electrolyser. The excess electricity production as depicted in the blue region of the graph. In such scenarios when the production of the electricity exceeds the consumption, the renewable energy generators are switched off. This process of not generating the excess electricity is also called as curtailment of the electricity.

In the given example in Figure 6, the capacity factor of the electrolyser increases from 45% to 75% by oversizing the wind installation, whereas, the LCOE only increases by ~20% (from 29 €/MWh to 37 €/MWh). The oversizing of the renewable power installations can also be a mix of energy between wind and solar where one compensates for the other during fluctuations times .

In this study, a LCOE analysis for various sizes of solar and wind has been conducted. It is considered that the electrolyser is coupled with a renewable installation that is a factor of 1 to 4 times greater than the electrolyser's total installed power. Moreover, an energy mix between wind and solar has also been considered with installation ratios of 75-25%, 50-50% or 20-75% respectively. The cases and the results of these exercises are given in the Appendix A.

3 Hydrogen Production

Beside the factors mentioned in the previous chapters, various additional parameters significantly influence the final cost of the hydrogen. These include the power consumption of the electrolyser which varies based on the technology employed, the capital cost of the electrolyser system which is discussed in the previous deliverable D6.2, the degradation of the stack, as it increases the power consumption of the overall system and the stack lifetime which adds to the capital cost as stack replacement costs are incurred. Various operational and economic assumptions concerning these factors are discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Electrolyser Assumptions

Electricity Consumption is the total electrical power required to split hydrogen and oxygen from the water molecule. Typically, the electricity consumption is expressed in kilowatt-hours (kWh) per unit of hydrogen produced, and it is a crucial factor in determining the overall cost of hydrogen production. Thus higher the production, more is the electricity consumption and it can also vary depending on the specific electrolyser technology. The values here are based on the previous deliverable in the NEWELY project.

Installed Electrolyser Power refers to the total power rating of all the electrolyser units that have been installed in a particular facility or location. It is typically measured in units of watts (W) or kilowatts (kW), and represents the maximum amount of electrical power that the electrolyser units can consume when operating at full capacity. The installed electrolyser power is an important factor in determining the hydrogen production capacity of a facility and the amount of renewable energy that is required to power it. Additionally, the installed electrolyser power is a key input parameter for estimating the capital and operational costs of an electrolyser plant. This value is based on the hydrogen production of 4000 kg/hr.

Degradation Rate of electrolysers is a measure of the reduction in efficiency or performance of the electrolyser over time. It is typically expressed as a percentage of the initial performance lost per thousand hours of operation (%/khrs) and is resulting in a higher electricity consumption of the electrolyser. The values from the relevant literature and NEWELY AEMWE operational targets are used here¹³.

Stack Lifetime is the expected operational lifetime of stack. After this period the stack would need to be replaced. The value of 80000 hours is used in this study.

Stack Cost refers to the cost of the stack component in an electrolyzer system per kilowatt of rated capacity. It is one of the key components of the overall capital cost of an electrolyzer system. The stack cost for PEMWE and AWE system along with its technical parameters are based on the literature, whereas that of AEMWE are based on the work done in the framework of the NEWELY project.

Balance of Plant Cost refers to components such as piping, valves, compressors, cooling systems, power electronics, control systems, safety equipment, and other auxiliary systems needed for the electrolysis process. The value for these costs are taken from deliverable D6.2.

Installation Cost refers to the cost associated with the installation and commissioning of the electrolyser system. This includes the cost of site preparation, equipment installation, and integration with other systems. An installation factor of 33% of the total expenditure is assumed to account for these costs³¹.

All these assumptions are summarized in the Table 3, as operational and economical parameters for the respective electrolyser technologies.

Table 3. Summary of major operational and economical assumption

Operational Parameter	Unit	AWE	PEMWE	AEM (100kW)	AEM (1 MW)	AEM (5 MW)
H ₂ production capacity	kg/hr	4000				
Electricity Consumption	kWh/kg H ₂	52.9	55.6	54.7	54.7	54.7
Installed Electrolyser Power	MW	214	225	221	221	221
Degradation Rate	%/khrs	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.09
Stack Lifetime	Hours	80000	80000	80000	80000	80000
Economical Parameter						
Stack Cost	€/kW	185	486	619	363	316
Balance of Plant Cost	€/kW	597*	528	528	528	528
Installation Cost	% of CAPEX	33	33	33	33	33

*including compression cost

3.2 Methodology for LCOH

The Levelised Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH) is estimated similarly as LCOE. The adjusted equation for LCOH is given as below,

$$LCOH (\text{€/MWh}) = \frac{I_o + I_r + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t + M_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{H_t}{(1+r)^t}} \quad \dots(3)$$

Where,

I_o is the total capital investment for the plant including the stack, BoP and installation costs

I_r is the cost of stack replacement.

E_t is the electricity expense in the year t . It is the product of the total electricity consumed annually (MWh/yr) and LCOE (€/MWh)

³¹ Manufacturing Cost Analysis for Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers, NREL, (2019)

M_t is the operational and maintenance cost of the plant in the year t , we assume these costs to be similar at 3% of the total capital investment as previously

H_t is the total hydrogen produced in the year t . This will vary depending on the mode of operation.

r is the discount rate to estimate the net present value of all the future cash flow. It is assumed to be 7% similar to LCOE

t is the total lifetime of the project, assumed to be 20 years

The cash flows over the entire lifetime of the plant are estimated and using the above equation the final LCOH for all the electrolyser technologies is calculated.

3.3 Results and Discussions

3.3.1 CAPEX

The total CAPEX of the electrolyser plant is assessed based on the costs provided earlier and the total rated power capacity for the system. This is the total capital that an electrolyser plant owner has to invest before the starting of the plant and needs to be paid upfront to complete the plant construction and set it into operation. The only exception is the cost of stack replacement which would need to be paid at the end of the stack lifetime.

The total CAPEX needed for the hydrogen production parts is given in Figure 7 below for the different water electrolysis technologies. The figure also provides the breakdown of the respective costs. The overall trend is similar to that observed in the system capital costs as discussed in D6.2. Meaning, the cost of AEMWE is expected to be in between that of AWE and PEMWE for MW scale stack sizes. However, for the 100 kW sizes owing to the small overall area of the cell and its components, the costs for AEMWE are higher than all the other technologies.

Figure 7. Total Capital Expenditure for each technology as a breakdown of various costs

This CAPEX is also affected by the total rated power capacity of the electrolyser. Although the total output of the hydrogen production is set at 4000 kg/hr, the system efficiency of each system

impacts the total power of electrolysis required. In this case, the AWE system benefits not only from the today lower CAPEX among the three water electrolysis technologies but also from the lower power consumption per kg of H₂ when compared to current efficiencies for PEM and AEM of the system

3.3.2 LCOH

Using the LCOH methodology described in section 3.2, the levelised cost of hydrogen is estimated. We evaluate this for two different scenarios of dynamic and steady state operation of the electrolysis plant.

Dynamic Operation:

The LCOE used in this study is based on connecting the electrolyzer to a wind capacity twice its power rating. As given in figure 8 below, LCOH for this scenario ranges from 3.6 to 4.8 €/kg, with an LCOE of 43 €/MWh and a capacity factor of 75%.

As discussed in the previous paragraph, with the given assumptions, H₂ from AWE, with a LCOH of 3.6 €/kg, stands out as the cheapest among the three analysed technologies being 16% lower than PEMWE and 6-7% lower than AEM depending on the stack size. However, AWE faces operational challenges, such as electrode degradation in the high pH environment and specially made BoP components to withstand the highly corrosive KOH solution. This can lead to some supply chain constraint in the future. The high volume of the KOH circulation also leads to a larger footprint of the overall plant. AWE also has longer start-up and ramp-up times, making it unsuitable for this dynamic operation.

As an alternative to AWE, AEMWE has a lower LCOH and can as PEM quickly respond to fluctuations, making it a good choice for dynamic operation. AEMWE uses an extremely dilute KOH, avoiding the electrode degradation issues faced by AWE. The LCOH for 1 MW and 5 MW AEMWE stacks is 3.9 €/kg and 3.8 €/kg, respectively, which is 10% lower than PEMWE, mainly due to the lower CAPEX and power consumption of AEMWE assumed for this study. Furthermore, AEMWE avoids the use of any critical materials, making it a potential environmentally friendly future alternative to PEMWE.

Figure 8. LCOH for electrolyser plants operating in dynamic mode

Static Mode:

The LCOE used in this analysis assumes that the electrolyzer is connected to a renewable energy mix that is four times the power of the electrolyzer system. This renewable energy mix is composed of 75% wind and 25% solar PV and has a capacity factor of 90%. The resulting LCOH for this scenario falls within the range of 4.8-5.9 €/kg as shown in Figure 9, which assumes an LCOE of 65.5 €/MWh.

Compared to the previous scenario, as the cost of electricity has increased, the LCOH for all the three technologies also increases. However, the relative cost trend among the technologies remains the same. AEMWE technology is therefore expected to have an LCOH that falls between PEMWE and AWE but, as already discussed in the previous scenario, with some advantages in terms of operability and reliability compared to AWE and with non PGM materials when compared to PEMWE.

Figure 9. LCOH for electrolyser plant operating in steady state mode

4 Sensitivity Analysis

The Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH) is a commonly used financial metric for evaluating the cost-effectiveness of hydrogen production technologies. However, LCOH estimates are subject to uncertainties, risks, and input parameter sensitivities. Therefore, sensitivity analyses are important for assessing the reliability and robustness of LCOH estimates. By varying one or more input parameters while holding others constant, sensitivity analyses evaluate the impact on LCOH and identify critical parameters requiring attention for further development and improvement.

The parameters on which sensitivity is performed in this study are as follows,

- Electricity Consumption - The overall electricity consumption per kg of hydrogen is varied at +/- 10% of the base case assumption.
- Stack Lifetime - Although the stack lifetime is assumed to be 80000 hours, it is a very optimistic assumption as the AEMWE is yet to achieve its performance maturity. For this sensitivity, the stack lifetime is varied from +/- 50 % of the base case assumption.
- Installation Cost - The installation cost is based on literature however in reality this cost could be higher. To account for this the installation cost varied between 20-50% of the total CAPEX.
- Operating Cost - The operating costs are not expected to have a significant effect on LCOH. These costs are varied from 1-5 % of the CAPEX
- Electricity Cost - The cost of electricity is one of the important factors that affect the LCOH. However, to account for the uncertainties in the LCOE evaluated in this study, the LCOE varied between +/-50% for both cases separately.
- CAPEX - The CAPEX of the system can significantly change the LCOH. To consider the associated uncertainties in the CAPEX of the system, the base case CAPEX assumption is varied in-between +/- 50%.

The base case assumption for the 1 MW AEMWE system was used as the basis for this sensitivity analysis. The results are given in the table below, where values are presented as Minimum < Lower < Base > Higher > Maximum (-50%, -25%, 0, 25%, 50% for a parametric variation of +/- 50%).

The input parameter values used for sensitivity analysis are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Input for Sensitivity Analysis

Parameter	Unit	Minimum	Lower	Base	Higher	Maximum
Electricity Consumption	kWh/kg H ₂	49.2	52.0	54.7	57.4	60.2
Stack Lifetime	Hours	40000	60000	80000	100000	120000
Installation Cost	% of CAPEX	20.0	25.0	33.0	40.0	50.0

Operating cost	% of CAPEX	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
Electricity Cost – Steady State	€/MWh	32.7	49.1	65.5	81.8	98.2
Electricity Cost – Dynamic	€/MWh	21.5	32.25	43	53.8	64.5
CAPEX	€/kW	431.0	646.5	862.0	1077.5	1293.0

The results of the sensitivity for both modes of operation are presented in a tornado chart in the figure below (figure 10).

As expected, the electricity cost and CAPEX of the system significantly vary the LCOH for both evaluated scenarios.

For the dynamic mode of operation, at the lowest electricity cost of 20€/MWh, LCOH drops below 3 €/kg. Whereas, at the highest cost of 64.5 €/MWh, the maximum observed value for LCOH is 5.1 €/kg. Similarly, a wide variation is observed for the steady-state operation.

If the CAPEX of the AEMWE system were to be 50% less than that estimated, the LCOH could decrease by 15% to 3.3 €/kg. Also, it increases by almost the same factor if the CAPEX for electrolyser was to be 50% more expensive. For the similar analysis the LCOH varies from 4.3 – 5.6 €/kg for steady state scenarios.

Please note that the electricity consumption assumed as the base case for AEMWE is based on the targeted power consumption of the system as agreed at the beginning of the project among all project partners. This is therefore one of the major factors which should be researched for and to be kept as low as possible.

Also for the stack lifetime, it is observed that reducing the stack lifetime does increase the LCOH due to more stack replacements. However, increasing the stack lifetime does not result in a similar trend.

The installation cost and operating cost do not affect the hydrogen cost considerably. These costs cannot be influenced by the development or performance improvement of the AEMWE system.

Figure 10. Sensitivity results for 1 MW AEMWE as base case

5 Conclusions

The port city of Hamburg in northern Germany has been selected as an ideal location for a medium-scale electrolysis-based hydrogen production plant with a capacity of 4000 kg/hr and a delivery pressure of 30 bar. The estimated installed electrolyzer power is 214 MW for AWE, 225 MW for PEMWE, and 221 MW for AEMWE. The LCOH for the AEMWE is estimated based on three different stack sizes, and it falls between the other two technologies. The wind and solar sizing for the electrolyzer is optimized for dynamic and steady operation modes.

In the dynamic mode of operation, the LCOH trend observed is PEMWE > AEMWE > AWE with values of 4.5 > 4 > 3.7 €/kg. It can be stated that H₂ from AEMWE can be 7 % cheaper than that from PEMWE mainly because AEM technology does not rely on precious and critical materials. On the other hand, AEMWE is 6 % more expensive than H₂ from AWE, this is due to the higher power consumption and a higher stack cost than the AWE system. However, for the dynamic mode of operation AEMWE system could be more suitable than traditional and cheaper AWE system due to its rapid response time and non-corrosive nature of operation.

In the steady state mode of operation the same LCOH trend is observed as for the previous scenario, i.e. PEMWE > AEMWE > AWE, only with higher H₂ cost: 5.5 > 5.1 > 4.8 €/kg.

The sensitivity results conclude that the electricity cost, CAPEX and consumptions per kg H₂ of the system are the most important factors influencing the final LCOH. Further developments and improvement in this direction can substantially reduce the cost of hydrogen.

Finally, it has to be considered that the LCOH calculated in this study is based on the assumption that technical and cost targets are achieved during ongoing and future AEMWE developments.

● **Appendix A: LCOE and Capacity factor for various electrolyser and renewable configurations**

Given below are various configurations of solar, wind and their mixes times the electrolyser unit.

Table A.1. Various configuration of Solar and Wind times the electrolyser plant

Parameter	Unit	S1	S2	S3	S4	W1	W2	W3	W4	
Solar	Times ELY	1	2	3	4					
Wind	Times ELY					1	2	3	4	
Parameter	Description	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9
Wind + Solar	Times ELY	2			3			4		
Power Split as % (Wind-Solar)	%	75-25	50-50	25-75	75-25	50-50	25-75	75-25	50-50	25-75

Figure A.1 shows the results of LCOE and capacity factors for all the configurations analysed. Out of which the W2 and M7 cases are chosen for the dynamic and static mode of electrolyser operation.

Figure A.1. Results for all the configuration showing the cost of electricity and capacity factors of the electrolyser

Part 2: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AEMWE	Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis
AWE	Alkaline Water Electrolysis
BPP	BiPolar Plate
CENmat	CUTTING-EDGE NANOMATERIALS UG (HAFTUNGSBESCHRÄNKT)
CM	ChloroMethylated
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
DABCO	1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane, N ₂ (C ₂ H ₄) ₃
DALY	Disability-Adjusted Life Year
DE	Germany
DLR	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUER LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV
EoL	End of Life
EPDM	Ethylene Propylene Diene Monomer rubber
GLO	Global
GO	Guarantee of Origin
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IMC-CAS	USTAV MAKROMOLEKULARNI CHEMIE AV CRVVI
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Chang
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MEA	Membrane Electrode Assembly
MPL	MicroPorous Layer
PEEK	PolyEther Ether Ketone
PEMWE	Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis
PPA	Power Procurement Agreement
ProPuls	PROPLUS GMBH
PSEBS	PolyStyrene-block-poly(Ethylene-ran-Butylene)-block-polyStyrene

PTL	Porous Transport Layer
PV	Photovoltaic
PVDF	Polyvinylidene fluoride
TEA	Techno Economic Analysis
WE	Water Electrolysis
WHS	WESTFALISCHE HOCHSCHULE GELSENKIRCHEN, BOCHOLT, RECKLINGHAUSEN

Summary

The objective of this LCA study is to assess the potential environmental impact of the **AEMWE** (Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis) system developed within the NEWELY project and to compare it to that of standard **PEMWE** (Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis) and **AWE** (Alkaline Water Electrolysis) from literature. Note that, at the time this report was written, the development of the NEWELY cell design was still in progress. Thus, this investigation assesses the impact of a not yet fully optimized NEWELY system.

The main takeaways are:

- **Electricity consumption and sourcing are confirmed to be the first optimization parameters** to reduce the environmental impact of electrolytic hydrogen. This conclusion is independent from the water electrolysis technology (NEWELY AEMWE, PEMWE or AWE) and from the selected LCIA methodologies among the three applied in the present study (IPCC 2021 GWP100y, ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint H, Eco-cost 2017). Moreover, this conclusion remains valid also if the electrolyser is powered by the renewable electricity of the lowest environmental impact.
- After electricity, **the stack is the second contributor to the environmental impact of hydrogen**. Its contribution is not negligible ($\geq 5\%$ cut-off) but substantially lower than that of electricity.
- **The lifetime of the components of the NEWELY AEMWE stack** is currently rather uncertain because a long-performance test has not been completed yet. Sensitivity analyses have shown that this parameter **strongly affects the comparison of the NEWELY AEMWE stack with the reference systems**. At parity of lifetime (“*target case*” scenario), the impact of the NEWELY AEMWE stack would be lower than (or similar to) that of the PEMWE stack and significantly lower than the AWE. However, under presently more realistic lifetime assumptions (“*base case*” scenario), the AEMWE would perform in between the PEMWE and the AWE stack. However, in this scenario the global warming potential and ReCiPe damage to resources of the NEWELY AEMWE stack are higher than those of the alkaline stack.
- **In the NEWELY AEM stack, the innovative CRM-free catalysts are much more environmentally friendly than the conventional catalysts** (Platinum and Iridium for PEMWE, and Nickel-based for AWE). Therefore, this development work is judged as extremely successful.

The innovative NEWELY membrane is slightly more impactful than those in the PEMWE and AWE stacks. However, due to the low contribution of the membrane to the total stack impact, it does not compromise the NEWELY system compared to the references.

On the other hand, the remaining major stack components of the NEWELY stacks (**stack frame, bipolar plate (BPP) and Porous Transport layer (PTL/MPL)**) **have substantially higher** impact than the corresponding elements in the reference systems. For global warming potential and damage to resources, this higher impact overcompensates the benefit achieved with the NEWELY catalysts. **PEEK** is identified as the driver for the higher impact of the NEWELY BPP, **steel and copper** for the higher impact of the NEWELY PTL and stack frame.

- Nevertheless, **the materials causing the higher impact of the NEWELY stack could be replaced**: instead of conventional PEEK, the corresponding version with lower environmental footprint developed by, e.g., Evonik could be tested; recycled copper and recycled steel could be used for the NEWELY PTL and stack frame.
- From a methodological point of view, both the multi-impact category LCIA (Life Cycle Impact Assessment) methodologies applied in this study (ReCiPe Endpoints and Eco-cost) show that global **warming potential alone is not sufficient to comprehensively describe the environmental impact of the NEWELY AEMWE stack**.

1 Introduction

The general objective of this LCA study was to assess the potential environmental impact of hydrogen produced according to the AEMWE (Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis) technology developed in the frame of the NEWELY funded project (Next Generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials).

More precisely, a comparative assessment was carried out by benchmarking hydrogen from the novel NEWELY AEMWE technology with that of hydrogen from the conventional reference technologies, AWE (Alkaline Water Electrolysis) and PEMWE (Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis). The comparison was performed at 5MW capacity. Based on this comparison some suggestions for improving the environmental performance of the NEWELY system were made.

The investigated product system consists in the production of hydrogen according to the selected water electrolysis technology, from extraction of the raw materials until the production gate (cradle-to-gate approach). The use phase of hydrogen was not included because it remains unchanged with the electrolysis technology itself.

The developed model includes the complete infrastructure (cell stacks, balance of stack and electrical equipment), electricity to operate the system, consumables and other utilities beyond electricity.

The environmental analysis has been performed starting from this complete system, then focusing on the stacks' comparison and finally on the NEWELY stack. Three life cycle assessment methodologies have been applied to benchmark the robustness of the conclusions. Moreover different scenarios for electricity and different assumptions for the lifetimes of the NEWELY stack components were investigated in the frame of sensitivity analyses.

2 Goal and scope definition

2.1 Goal definition

The **general objective** of this study is to assess the potential environmental impact of hydrogen produced according to the AEMWE (Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis) technology developed in the frame of the NEWELY funded project (Next Generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials).

More precisely, a **comparative assessment** was carried out by benchmarking hydrogen from the novel NEWELY AEMWE technology with that of hydrogen from the conventional reference technologies, AWE (Alkaline Water Electrolysis) and PEMWE (Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis). The comparison was performed at 5MW capacity. Based on this comparison some suggestions for improving the environmental performance of the NEWELY system were made.

The **target audience** of this report includes scientists and experts in the field of water electrolysis production and use (technical audience) as well as non-technical audience. This audience might possess a general understanding of the LCA methodology but not necessarily operational practice in this field.

According to ISO 14044 (paragraph 3.6) this study is **not a comparative assertion to be disclosed to the public**. Therefore an external critical review is not mandatory and was not carried out. Nevertheless, an **internal review** was conducted in Air Liquide.

2.2 Scope definition

2.2.1 Product system, functional unit, geographical and temporal scope

The investigated **product system** consists in the production of hydrogen according to the selected water electrolysis technology, from extraction of the raw materials until the production gate (cradle-to-gate approach). Further compression, transportation and use of hydrogen are outside the system boundaries. Note that those steps are independent from the selected WE (water electrolysis) technology and won't affect the comparison of the three WEs.

The investigated process system is schematically illustrated in Figure 1. It includes the complete infrastructure (cell stacks, balance of stack and electrical equipment), electricity to operate the system, consumables and other utilities beyond electricity. Details can be found in the section "Life cycle inventory".

The **declared unit** is 1kg of hydrogen at production gate conditions. The NEWELY AEM stack can deliver hydrogen at higher pressure (e.g. 40bar) than the classical AWE and PEMWE technologies. However, this pressure difference was not considered in the present study. In fact the electricity consumption required to compress hydrogen and level up its pressure among the three WE technologies is negligible compared to that required to operate the electrolysis plant.

Figure 1 Product system and process units

The current study is focused on a **present scenario (year 2020)**. This is the reference year of the most recent dataset available in LCA databases for electricity, which is the dominant driver of the impact of electrolytic hydrogen.

The **geographical scenario** is exclusively defined by the selected dataset for electricity. The main cases refer to **Germany**, but additional cases with other geographies could be easily implemented.

2.2.2 Data source

The data sources for each process unit are described below. The corresponding inventories are documented in the section “Assignment of LCI to datasets.”

2.2.2.1 Stack

For the **NEWELY AEM stack**, materials types and installed amounts were provided by the project Partners responsible for the development of the various components:

- Membrane/Ionomer: Jan Žitka (IMC-CAS)
- Catalysts: Schwan Hosseiny (CENmat)
- PTL/MTL: Regine Reißner (DLR)
- Stack development and component integration: Jeffrey Roth (WHS), Philipp Neuhaus (ProPuls)

The Partners already accounted for the scale-up between the 2kW prototype developed in the NEWELY project and the 5MW industrial size system, which is the object of this study. While the large majority of those data were collected in the NEWELY deliverable D6.1³², changes to account for the following development were accounted for. This refers mainly to the stack frame materials and amounts.

³² NEWELY D6.1 (Confidential) 30.06.2021, *AEMWE requirements and technical, financial and techno operational KPIs*

For the **AWE and PEMWE** technologies data were taken exclusively from literature. For the AWE system the Koj's publications^{33,34,35} were used. For the PEMWE system different literature sources were compared^{36,37,38,39,40,41} and the most relevant data selected.

2.2.2.2 Balance of Stack

Installed steel amounts were taken from Koj publications^{3,4,5} and incremented by 2% to account for the additional equipment. Steel amounts for the deoxo and driers units, as well as polyethylene for the water tank, were taken from internal projects.

The only adaptation made between the three WE technologies consists in removing the steel for the KOH tank for the PEMWE.

2.2.2.3 Power transformers and rectifier

Materials and energy data were taken from two Environmental Product Declaration by ABB (reference EPD 63 MVA⁴² and 20 MVA⁴³).

No modifications of those components were implemented for the three WE systems.

2.2.2.4 Electricity consumption

For the **NEWELY AEMWE system**, the electricity consumption was estimated by the project Partners. Please note that at the time of the present LCA report, the NEWELY system was not already subjected to extensive testing. Therefore the estimated electricity consumption is a preliminary figure, which might require some adjustments.

³³ J. C. Koj et al., STE Research Report 01/2015, *Life Cycle Assessment of improved high pressure alkaline electrolysis*

³⁴ J. C. Koj et al., *Energies* 10 (2017) 860, *Site-Dependent Environmental Impacts of Industrial Hydrogen Production by Alkaline Water Electrolysis*

³⁵ J.C. Koj et al., *Energy Procedia* 75 (2015) 2871, *Life Cycle assessment of improved high pressure alkaline electrolysis*

³⁶ A. Mayyas et al., NREL 2018 report, *Manufacturing Cost Analysis for Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers*

³⁷ K. Bareiß et al, *Applied Energy* 237, 2019, 862-872, *Life cycle assessment of hydrogen from proton exchange membrane water electrolysis in future energy systems*

³⁸ D. Bessarabov et al., *PEM Water Electrolysis*, 2018 Elsevier

³⁹ F.J. Hackemüller et al., *Advanced Engineering Materials* 21(6), 2019, 1801201, *Manufacturing of Large-Scale Titanium Porous Transport Layers for Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Electrolysis by Tape Casting*

⁴⁰ C. Liu et al., *Electrochemistry Communications*, 97, 2018, 96-99, *Performance enhancement of PEM electrolyzers through iridium-coated titanium porous transport layers*

⁴¹ S. Shiva, *Material Science for Energy Technologies*, 2(3), 2019, 442-454, *Hydrogen production by PEM water electrolysis – A review*

⁴² CERTIFIED EPD (S-P 00019, <http://www.environdec.com>), *Power transformer TrafoStar 63 MVA*.

⁴³ CERTIFIED ENVIRONMENTAL PRODUCT DECLARATION (S-P-00056, <http://www.environdec.com>), *Large Distribution Transformer 16/20 MVA (ONAN/ONAF)*

For **AWE and PEMWE**, the typical electricity consumption was derived from a literature survey carried out within the NEWELY project (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Electricity consumption for AWE and PEMWE (from NEWELY D6.1³⁴)

2.2.2.5 Operation without electricity

The majority of the utilities and consumables associated with this process unit were taken from Air Liquide internal projects.

The only adaptation made between the three WE technologies is the KOH consumption, which is not required for PEMWE and only in a tiny concentration (0.1M) for the NEWELY AEMWE system.

2.2.3 Data Quality

The different nature of the data sources for the different process units of the three WE technologies has a direct impact on the corresponding data quality.

At **stack** level, the source of the information for NEWELY AEM stack is very specific and the best possible, since provided by the project partners developing the system components. On the other hand, this AEM system is still in development and changes are likely to occur in the future. On the contrary, the AWE and PEMWE are generic but mature systems.

For the **electricity consumption**, the extended testing of the NEWELY unit has not been done yet. Therefore, the operational data are still affected by uncertainty.

For the remaining process units (electrical equipment, balance of cell stacks, operation beyond electricity) identical or very similar models were applied for all three WE technologies, so that the same data quality applies.

2.2.4 Sensitivity analyses

Sensitivity analyses were carried out to cope with the uncertainty related to the input data of the three technologies (AEMWE, PEMWE and AWE).

The **lifetime of the components** of the in development **NEWELY AEMWE stack** is highly uncertain as a long test under industrial conditions is still pending. To account for this uncertainty, two cases were set-up, the “**base case**” and the “**target case**”. In the *target case* it was assumed that the lifetime of the AEMWE components would reach that of the PEMWE and AWE mature technologies. This represents a future scenario. In the *base case* scenario the lifetime of the AEMWE stack components was assumed to be three or four times shorter than that of the corresponding components of PEMWE and AWE. This case is more representative of a present scenario. Table 1 summarizes the lifetime assumptions for the plant and stack components for the NEWELY AEMWE stack, as well for the two reference systems, PEMWE and AWE. The latter were taken from a survey made within the NEWELY project and documented in deliverable D6.1³⁴ (see Figure 3).

	Lifetime (years)		
	AWE, PEMWE	AEMWE base case	AEMWE target case
Plant	20	20	20
Membrane, electrodes, gasket	10	3	10
PTL	20	5	20
BPP	20	5	20
Stack frame	20	5	20

Table 1 Lifetime assumptions

Figure 3 Stack lifetime for AWE (blue bar; dark blue represents the most likely value) and PEMWE (yellow bar; dark yellow represents the most likely value) from NEWELY D6.1³⁴

For the PEMWE and AWE systems, sensitivity analyses were carried with respect to the emissions factors for the catalyst metals. Those parameters were selected after the first calculation run because they contribute remarkably to the LCIA results.

CASES → ↓ PARAMETER	PEMWE main case	PEMWE sensitivity	AWE main case	AWE sensitivity
Emission factor - Ir	GaBi	Ecoinvent-based	--	--
Emission factor - Pt	GaBi	Ecoinvent-based	--	--
Emission factor - Ni	---	---	Ecoinvent	GaBi

Table 2 Sensitivity analyses for PEMWE and AWE

2.2.5 Allocation

In the main calculation, heat was considered as dissipated and co-produced oxygen as vented to the atmosphere. Therefore, as in this scenario the system is not multi-functional, **allocation was not required**.

Nevertheless, for the **NEWELY system** an **additional case** was made where **oxygen was considered as a product**. For this additional case the environmental saving caused by the avoided additional production of oxygen was assessed (see paragraph “effect of oxygen valorization”).

2.2.6 LCIA methodologies

For the present investigation, three LCIA methodologies were applied:

- IPCC 2021 GWP 100a
- Eco-cost 2017
- ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H), v1.1

The LCA software applied for the calculations is **SimaPro (version 9.3.0.3)**.

IPCC 2021 GWP 100a (Global Warming Potential) is the most recent version of the method developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to quantify the global warming potential of a product (in kgCO₂eq).

On the contrary Eco-cost and ReCiPe are two multi-impact category methodologies: beside climate change impact they include many other impacts.

Eco-cost is a monetary single indicator system in LCA. Eco-costs are the costs of the environmental burden of a product on the basis of the prevention of that burden. They are the costs which should be made to reduce the environmental pollution and materials depletion to a level which is in line with the carrying capacity of our earth. The eco-costs should be regarded as hidden obligations: this is also called “external costs”. The business relevance of eco-costs is that it is the financial risk of non-compliance with future governmental regulation. The structure of eco-

cost is shown in Figure 4. Further details about this method are available in the TUDelft webpage⁴⁴.

Figure 4 The eco-cost structure⁴⁶

ReCiPe is recognized as one of the most recent and updated impact assessment methods available to LCA practitioners.⁴⁵

ReCiPe⁴⁶ is a damage-based method which translates the life cycle inventory into several environmental impacts, 18 midpoints and 3:

- Damage to human health (DALY),
- Damage to ecosystems (species x yr),
- Damage to resources (USD2013).

Figure 5 provides an overview of the link between midpoints and the three areas of protection.

⁴⁴ <https://www.ecocostsvalue.com/eco-costs/>

⁴⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/biodiversity/business/assets/pdf/tool-descriptions/RECiPe%20and%20BioScope%20summary%20description.pdf>

⁴⁶ <https://www.rivm.nl/en/life-cycle-assessment-lca/recipe>

Figure 5 ReCiPe mid- and endpoints ⁴⁷

2.2.7 LCA tools

Emission factors for secondary data were mainly extracted from **Ecoinvent 3.8** (allocation cut-off by classification) using the software **SimaPro 9.3.0.3**-Jan 2022.

When datasets were not available in Ecoinvent, emissions factors were possibly extracted from **GaBi 10.6.1.35**-Mar 2022. Finally, if datasets were neither available in Ecoinvent nor in GaBi, proxies were set-up or taken from Ecoinvent. The different source of those secondary data is indicated by colour codes in the inventory tables (Table 4 to Table 6).

2.2.8 Report format

The report format selected for this study is a simplified report, free from the formalism required in an ISO-compliant report.

2.2.9 Limitations of the study

The main limitations of the study are listed here below.

- The performance of the NEWELY AEMWE system (i.e. **electricity consumption**) is currently not known because an extensive test has not been yet carried out.
- The **lifetime of the NEWELY AEM stack components** (membrane, catalysts, etc) is still uncertain. To cope with this uncertainty, LCA results have been calculated for two sets of lifetime values (see paragraph “sensitivity analyses”).
- For the PEMWE model the **emission factors for Iridium and Platinum** are highly uncertain. For the main calculation those factors have been taken from GaBi. Nevertheless, such datasets are rather obsolete and work is in progress to produce an update. To get a rough estimation of the effect of such uncertainty on the LCA results for hydrogen from PEMWE,

two alternative datasets for Pt and Ir were created in Ecoinvent (see paragraph “sensitivity analyses”).

- Some input data about the preparation of the NEWELY AEM catalysts could not be disclosed because of confidentiality reasons. As a consequence generic datasets had to be set up for the generic inputs, such as “reaction agent” and “acid. Note that due to the very low contribution of these inputs to the overall results, this limitation is assumed to be acceptable.
- For some inputs of the LCA models, datasets could not be found neither in Ecoinvent nor in GaBi. In this case some proxies were set-up. Note that due to the marginal contribution of those inputs this limitation is assumed to be acceptable.

3 Life Cycle Inventory

3.1 Product system and process units

Figure 6 shows the **tree model** used to describe the product system under study. At the top is hydrogen, the desired product. In the second level of the tree are the process units. The activities included are listed below each of them.

In the result section, the overall process system of Figure 6 is called “**The complete system**” to distinguish it from the stack level.

For the **end-of-life** the following assumptions were made:

- **Materials:** 90% of all metals (steel, nickel, copper, aluminium) are recycled. The remaining 10% of the metals and all other non-metallic materials are landfilled. A credit was not given to hydrogen due to the recycling of the metals but at least the environmental burdens associated with the metal disposal (landfilling) were not charged to hydrogen. The distance between the electrolyser plant location and the dismantling/recycling location was assumed to be 500 km. The same assumptions were applied for the power transformers and balance of cell stack.
- **Deoxo-catalyst:** in the absence of precise info, it was assumed that the deoxo-catalyst is disposed as hazardous waste.
- **KOH:** in the absence of precise info, it was assumed that KOH is first neutralized with sulphuric acid and the remaining liquid sent to the water treatment.

Figure 6 Hydrogen production: process units and included activities

As indicated in Figure 6, in the LCA models some process units are more affected than others by the selected WE technology (AWE, PEMWE or AEMWE):

- “cell stack” (and potentially “electricity”) significantly vary,
- “balance of cell stack” and “operation without electricity” slightly change,
- “Transformers and rectifier” do not change.

The changes, as well as the source of the data, are summarized in paragraph “data sources”.

3.2 Cell stacks differences

Figure 7 shows the schematic of a AEMWE cell configuration with its components.

Figure 7 Schematic of a AEMWE cell configuration⁴⁷ with MPL/MPL

Table 3 compares the three stacks (NEWELY AEM, PEM and alkaline) in terms of materials types, electricity consumption and KOH concentration. The amounts of the various installed materials are shown in figure 9.

The most interesting observations are:

- The PEMWE stack is much more **compact** than the AWE stack. The NEWELY AEM stack is in between, more close to PEMWE in the *target scenario*, more close to AWE in the *base case scenario*. For the definition of the scenarios see paragraph “sensitivity analysis”.
- In all three systems, **stainless steel** is the dominating material. However, after steel the most abundant material is **PEEK for AEMWE, Nickel for AWE, and Titanium for PEMWE**. The distribution of such materials among the various stack components is shown in the pie-charts of Figure 8.
- According to the literature survey made within the NEWELY project, the electricity consumption of PEMWE and AWE is rather similar (see Figure 2). The electricity consumption in the NEWELY AEMWE system is expected to be quite close as well.
- KOH is not required for the operation of the PEMWE stack, while 4.5M KOH (conc. 25%) is used in AWE. For the NEWELY AEM system a much smaller KOH concentration (0.1M) is needed.

⁴⁷ F. Razmjooei et al., Joule 5, 1776–1799, 2021, *Increasing the performance of an anion-exchange membrane electrolyzer operating in pure water with a nickel-based microporous layer*

	NEWELY AEMWE	AWE	PEMWE
MEMBRANE	PSEBS CM DABCO	Zirfon	Nafion
ANODE	CMR-free catalyst	Ni	Ir (2.0 mg/cm ²)
CATHODE	CMR-free catalyst	Ni-Raney	Pt (0.5 mg/cm ²)
CELL FRAME	Steel/Ni (PTL/MPL) PEEK/Steel (BPP)	Ni/Steel (BPP)	Ti (BPP + PTL cathodic)
SEAL	EPDM/PEEK	Graphite + nitrile butadiene + aramid fibers + PTFE	Polyphenylene Sulfide + Glass fibers
STACK FRAME	Steel/Cu/PEEK	Steel/Cu	Steel/Cu/Ni
ELECTRICITY (kWh/kg H₂)	54.7	52.9	55.6
KOH conc	0.1 M	25% (4.5M)	no

Table 3 Comparison of stacks: materials, electricity consumption and KOH concentration

Figure 8 Materials types and amounts in the NEWELY AEMWE, PEMWE and AWE stacks. Inserts: distribution of the materials in the stack components.

3.3 Inventories

The inventories of the three WE “complete systems” can be found, together with the corresponding selected datasets, in the paragraph “assignment of LCI to datasets”. For the NEWELY AEM system they refer to the *base case* scenario.

3.4 Electricity scenarios

Electricity is the determining source of environmental impact for electrolytic hydrogen. Thus, to evaluate the impact of hydrogen three different electricity scenarios were selected:

- Electricity from the German grid (year 2020),
- Electricity from wind off-shore in Germany,
- Photovoltaic electricity power in a European southern country.

The absolute impact of these three electricity types is shown in Table 4. Figure 9 shows the relative impact of wind and PV power with respect to the German grid, as well as their availability.

ELECTRICITY, ASOLUTE IMPACT		DE, grid 2020	South EU, PV	DE, Wind offshore
GWP	(gCO ₂ eq / kWh)	408	35	8
Ecocost	(€ / kWh)	0.076	0.014	0.005
ReCiPe H - HH	(DALY / kWh)	5.73E-07	1.06E-07	2.82E-08
ReCiPe H - Ecos	(Species x year / kWh)	1.46E-09	1.87E-10	4.09E-11
ReCiPe H - Res.	(USD / kWh)	2.42E-02	2.09E-03	6.50E-04

Table 4 Environmental impact of electricity

Figure 9 Relative impact of PV and wind power compared to the German grid

Overall, the global picture is consistent across the different LCIA methodologies: the impact of PV power is 10-20% of that of the German grid, while that of wind power is circa 5-10% of it. The three types of electricity selected for this study are also characterised by a very different availability: 98% for the grid, 49% for wind (rounded to 50% in the results figures) and 15% for PV. In the main LCA calculation for H₂ the availability of the electricity was assumed to determine the availability of the electrolysis plant. 98% plant availability was assumed for the case with grid electricity. In the alternative scenarios with wind electricity the availability of the electrolysis plant was also assumed to be 98%. This would correspond to a GO/PPA configuration.

4 Life Cycle Impact assessment

4.1 Assignment of LCI to datasets

To assign the life cycle inventories to the selected impact categories, a LCA model was made (Table 5 to Table 7 for the AEMWE, PEMWE and AWE complete systems, respectively). Note that for the AEMWE case the inventory refers to the base case scenario. Cells in pink indicate inputs for which specific databases could not be found neither in Ecoinvent nor in GaBi. Proxies were used instead. Inputs in green were combined with GaBi databases. For all other entries Ecoinvent datasets were applied.

NEWELY AEM complete system: inventory (base case) & LCA model

PROCESS UNIT	COMPONENT	INPUT	UNIT	AMOUNT (Unit/kg H2)	DATASET
STACK	MEMBRANE	PSEBS	kg	1,49E-05	Polystyrene, high impact {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		DABCO (DBC)	kg	3,00E-06	.ROB_DABCO (created by Roberta)
		Processing of polymer to membrane	kg	1,79E-05	Injection moulding {RER} processing Cut-off, S
		Chloroform	kg	2,83E-04	Trichloromethane {RER} market for trichloromethane Cut-off, S
		Dimethoxymethane	kg	2,99E-05	.ROB Dimethoxymethane
		Zinc chloride	kg	3,58E-06	.ROB_ZnCl2 from adapted Ecoinvent process "Iron (III) chloride, without water, in 40% solution state {RoW} iron (III) chloride production, product in 40% solution state Cut-off, U"
		Tetrachlorosilane	kg	5,97E-06	Silicon tetrachloride {RoW} market for silicon tetrachloride Cut-off, S
		Toluene	kg	4,78E-05	Toluene, liquid {RER} market for toluene, liquid Cut-off, S
		Ethanol	kg	1,41E-03	Ethanol, without water, in 99.7% solution state, from fermentation {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		CO2 from solvent combustion	kg	3,16E-04	CO2 to air (fossil)
	NaOH for HCl neutralization	kg	2,42E-03	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	
	CATHODE	Reaction agent (unspecified)	kg	1,42E-06	Ecoinvent dataset
		Ultrapure water	liter	2,99E-04	.ROB_Water, ultrapure {DE} production Cut-off, U
		Reaction agent (unspecified)	kg	2,36E-05	.ROB_Chemical generic (organic & inorganic)
		Acid (unspecified)	liter	1,96E-04	.ROB_Acid mix (organic + inorganic)
		Argon	kg	1,67E-05	Argon, crude, liquid {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Ethanol	kg	8,06E-07	Ethanol, without water, in 99.7% solution state, from fermentation {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	ANODE	Reaction agent (unspecified)	kg	1,43E-05	Ecoinvent dataset
		Reaction agent (unspecified)	kg	5,18E-06	Ecoinvent dataset
		Ultrapure water	liter	2,18E-03	.ROB_Water, ultrapure {DE} production Cut-off, U
		Reaction agent (unspecified)	kg	2,35E-05	.ROB_Chemical generic (organic & inorganic)
		Argon	kg	2,11E-06	Argon, crude, liquid {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	PTL/MPL	Ethanol	kg	5,87E-04	Ethanol, without water, in 99.7% solution state, from fermentation {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Nickel	kg	4,01E-05	Nickel, class 1 {GLO} market for nickel, class 1 Cut-off, S
		Carbon	kg	1,00E-05	Carbon black {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Stainless steel	kg	2,52E-03	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Argon	kg	7,45E-04	Argon, crude, liquid {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Hydrogen	kg	3,10E-06	.ROB_Hydrogen_SMR base case_ only DE_NG
		Helium	kg	1,57E-05	Helium {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	BPP	Electricity per manufacturing	kWh	4,57E-03	Electricity, high voltage {Europe without Switzerland} market group for Cut-off, S
		Stainless Steel	kg	2,99E-04	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Stainless Steel	kg	5,35E-04	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	CELL SEAL	PEEK	kg	1,54E-03	PEEK (GaBi)
		EPDM	kg	1,72E-04	EPDM (GaBi)
	CURRENT COLLECTOR	PEEK	kg	4,76E-05	PEEK (GaBi)
		Copper	kg	5,58E-04	Copper, cathode {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	END PLATE	Stainless Steel	kg	7,72E-04	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		PEEK	kg	7,46E-05	PEEK (Gabi)
	STACK FRAME	Stainless Steel	kg	1,59E-03	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	MANUFACTURING	Electricity per manufacturing	kWh	2,75E-03	Electricity, high voltage {Europe without Switzerland} market group for Cut-off, S
		Heat (to manufacture of the system)	kWh	3,15E-03	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {RER} market group for Cut-off, S
		Steam (to manufacture of the system)	kWh	2,50E-05	Heat, from steam, in chemical industry {RER} market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry Cut-off, S

	EoL	Recycling of metal	kg	5,68E-03	
		Disposal (landfilling)	kg	8,21E-04	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S
		Transportation	tkm	4,09E-03	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S
BALANCE OF STACKS	MATERIALS & MANUFACTURING	Stainless Steel	kg	1,23E-03	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Water tank polyethylene	kg	5,83E-06	Polyethylene, high density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Processing of steel to manufacture the equipments	kg	1,23E-03	Metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing {RER} processing Cut-off, S
		Processing of plastic to manufacture the water tanks	kg	5,83E-06	Extrusion of plastic sheets and thermoforming, inline {RoW} processing Cut-off, S
	EoL	Recycling of metals	kg	1,10E-03	
		Disposal (landfilling)	kg	1,23E-04	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S
		Incineration plastic water tank	kg	5,83E-06	Waste polypropylene {RoW} treatment of waste polypropylene, municipal incineration Cut-off, S
		Transportation	tkm	6,17E-04	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S
	MATERIALS & MANUFACTURING	Steel for KOH filter & KOH tank	kg	5,16E-04	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Processing of steel to manufacture the equipments	kg	5,16E-04	Metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing {RER} processing Cut-off, S
OPERATION	UTILITIES & CONSUMABLES	KOH	kg	3,20E-05	Potassium hydroxide {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		H2SO4 to neutralize lye	kg	2,86E-05	Sulfuric acid {RER} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, S
		Treatment of wastewater after lye neutralization	m3	9,59E-08	.ROB_Wastewater, COPY only for DE_average {CA-QC} treatment of wastewater, average, capacity 1.6E8l/year Cut-off, U
		Electricity	kWh	54,70	1 kWh_UBA_Electricity from wind, {GLO}, 8MW turbine, offshore Cut-off, U (of project Ibra Training)
		Feed Water (deionized)	kg	10,0	.ROB_Water, ultrapure {DE} production Cut-off, U
		Nitrogen	kg	0,00029	Nitrogen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, S
		Cooling water	kg	45	.ROB_Cooling water {DE}
		Pd in deoxo catalyst (Pd/supported)	kg	6,80E-08	Palladium {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Al2O3 in deoxo catalyst	kg	2,26E-05	Aluminium oxide, metallurgical {IAI Area, EU27 & EFTA} market for aluminium oxide, metallurgical Cut-off, S
		Driers adsorbents	kg	1,94E-05	Zeolite, powder {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT		Disposal of Deoxocatalyst	kg	2,27E-05	Hazardous waste, for underground deposit {RoW} treatment of hazardous waste, underground deposit Cut-off, S
		Inverter	p	1,29E-06	Inverter, 500kW {RER} production Cut-off, S
		HV-MV transformer	p	1,02E-08	AEL_0b Transformer 63 MVA (HV to MV) - updated after switch to Ecoinvent 3.8
		MV-LV transformer	p	3,22E-08	AEL_0a Transformer 20 MVA (MV to LV) - updated to Ecoinvent 3.8

Table 5 NEWELY AEM complete system: inventory (base case) and LCA model

PEMWE complete system: inventory & LCA model					
PROCESS UNIT	COMPONENT	INPUT	UNIT	AMOUNT (Unit/kg H2)	DATASET

STACK	MEMBRANE	Nafion 117	kg	1.57E-05	GaBi, US: Nafion (estimation) ts
	ANODE	Iridium	kg	6.54E-07	ZA: Iridium Sphera
	CATHODE	Platinum	kg	1.63E-07	GLO: Platinum mix Sphera
		Carbon	kg	7.01E-08	Carbon black {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	CELL FRAME	Titanium (BPP)	kg	2.95E-04	Titanium {GLO} market for titanium Cut-off, S
		Titanium (PTL cathodic)	kg	1.55E-05	Titanium {GLO} market for titanium Cut-off, S
		Carbon paper (PTL anodic)	kg	2.16E-06	Carbon black {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	GASKET	Polyphenylene Sulfide PPS (60%wt)	kg	6.636E-06	Polyphenylene sulfide {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Glass fibers (40%wt)	kg	4.42E-06	Glass fibre {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	STACK FRAME	Copper (current collectors)	kg	9.38E-06	Copper, cathode {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Steel unalloyed (Endplants + stack frame)	kg	6.20E-04	Steel, unalloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Nickel (Endplates)	kg	2.51E-05	Nickel, class 1 {GLO} market for nickel, class 1 Cut-off, S
	MANUFACTURING	Total electricity per manufacturing	kWh	1.25E-03	Electricity, high voltage {Europe without Switzerland} market group for Cut-off, S
		Heat (for system manufacturing)	kWh	3.20E-03	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {RER} market group for Cut-off, S
		Steam (for system manufacturing)	kWh	2.54E-05	Heat, from steam, in chemical industry {RER} market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry Cut-off, S
EoL	Disposal (landfilling)	kg	1.25E-04	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S	
	Transportation	tkm	4.97E-04	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S	
BALANCE OF STACKS	MATERIALS & MANUFACTURING	Total steel chromium	kg	1.20E-03	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Water tank polyethylene	kg	5.83E-06	Polyethylene, high density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Processing of steel to manufacture the equipments	kg	1.20E-03	Metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing {RER} processing Cut-off, S
		Processing of plastic to manufacture the water tanks	kg	5.83E-06	Extrusion of plastic sheets and thermoforming, inline {RoW} processing Cut-off, S
	EoL	Disposal (landfilling)	kg	1.20E-04	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S
		Incineration plastic water tank	kg	5.83E-06	Waste polypropylene {RoW} treatment of waste polypropylene, municipal incineration Cut-off, S
		Transportation	tkm	6.04E-04	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S
OPERATION	UTILITIES AND CONSUMABLES	Electricity	kWh	5.56E+01	1 kWh_UBA_Electricity from wind, {GLO}, 8MW turbine, offshore Cut-off, U (of project Ibra Training)
		Feed Water (deionized)	kg	1.00E+01	.ROB_Water, ultrapure {DE} production Cut-off, U
		Nitrogen	kg	2.90E-04	Nitrogen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, S
		Cooling water	kg	4.50E+01	.ROB_Cooling water {DE}
		Pd in deoxo catalyst (Pd/supported)	kg	6.800E-08	Palladium {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Al2O3 in deoxo catalyst	kg	2.26E-05	Aluminium oxide, metallurgical {IAI Area, EU27 & EFTA} market for aluminium oxide, metallurgical Cut-off, S
		Driers adsorbents	kg	1.94E-05	Zeolite, powder {GLO} market for Cut-off, S

		Disposal of Deoxocatalyst	kg	2.27E-05	Hazardous waste, for underground deposit {RoW} treatment of hazardous waste, underground deposit Cut-off, S
ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT		Inverter	p	1.31E-06	Inverter, 500kW {RER} production Cut-off, S
		HV-MV transformer	p	1.04E-08	AEL_0b_Transformer 63 MVA (HV to MV) - updated after switch to Ecoinvent 3.8
		MV-LV transformer	p	3.27E-08	AEL_0a_Transformer 20 MVA (MV to LV) - updated to Ecoinvent 3.8

Table 6 PEMWE complete system: inventory and LCA model

AWE						
PROCESS UNIT	COMPONENT	INPUT	UNIT	AMOUNT (Unit/kg H2)	DATASET	
STACK	MEMBRANE (Zirfon)	Polyphenylene sulfide	kg	3.53E-05	.ROB_Polyphenylene sulfide {GLO} market for Cut-off, U_with oil in materials (for eco-costs)	
		Polysulfone	kg	2.70E-05	.ROB_Polysulfone {GLO} market for Cut-off, U_with oil in materials (for eco-costs)	
		N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone	kg	1.35E-04	.ROB_N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone {RER} production Cut-off, U_with oil in materials for eco-costs	
		Zirconium oxide	kg	1.14E-04	Zirconium oxide {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	
	ANODE (Nickel)	Nickel	kg	1.18E-03	Nickel, class 1 {GLO} market for nickel, class 1 Cut-off, S	
	CATHODE (Raney Nickel)	Nickel	kg	1.10E-03	Nickel, class 1 {GLO} market for nickel, class 1 Cut-off, S	
		Aluminium	kg	9.34E-05	Aluminium, primary, ingot {IAI Area, EU27 & EFTA} market for Cut-off, S	
		Carbon monoxide	kg	3.11E-05	Carbon monoxide {RER} market for Cut-off, S	
	CELL FRAME (= BPP)	Steel unalloyed	kg	2.50E-03	Steel, unalloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	
		Nickel	kg	4.38E-04	Nickel, class 1 {GLO} market for nickel, class 1 Cut-off, S	
	GASKET	Polytetrafluoroethylene	kg	8.09E-06	.ROB_Tetrafluoroethylene {GLO} market for Cut-off, U_with oil in material (for ecocost)	
		Graphite	kg	4.46E-05	Graphite {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	
		Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene	kg	1.66E-05	.ROB_Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer {RER} production Cut-off, U_with oil in materials (for eco-cost)	
		Lubricating oil	kg	4.98E-08	.ROB_Lubricating oil {GLO} market for Cut-off, U_with oil in materials (for eco-costs)	
		Aniline (Aramid fibers)	kg	5.08E-06	.ROB_Aniline {GLO} market for Cut-off, U_with oil in materials (for eco-costs)	
		Acetic anhydride (Aramid fibers)	kg	5.60E-06	.ROB_Acetic anhydride {GLO} market for acetic anhydride Cut-off, U_with oil in material (for eco-cost)	
		Terephthalic acid (Aramid fibers)	kg	9.13E-06	.ROB_Purified terephthalic acid {GLO} market for Cut-off, U_with oil in materials (for eco-costs)	
		Nitric acid (Aramid fibers)	kg	3.42E-06	Nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state {RER w/o RU} market for nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, S	
		Hydrochloric acid (Aramid fibers)	kg	1.35E-05	Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RER} market for Cut-off, S	
		STACK FRAME	Copper	kg	1.04E-04	Copper, cathode {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	Steel unalloyed		kg	8.09E-03	Steel, unalloyed {GLO} market for Cut-off, S	
	MANUFACTURING	Total electricity per manufacturing	kWh	9.76E-04	Electricity, high voltage {Europe without Switzerland} market group for Cut-off, S	
		Water for membrane manufacturing	kg	1.16E-02	Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised Cut-off, S	
		Heat (assumed to manufacture of the system)	kWh	3.04E-03	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {RER} market group for Cut-off, S	
		Steam (assumed to manufacture of the system)	kWh	2.42E-05	Heat, from steam, in chemical industry {RER} market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry Cut-off, S	
	EoL	Disposal (landfilling)	kg	1.80E-03	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S	
		Transportation	tkm	6.98E-03	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S	
			Total steel chromium	kg	1.87E-03	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for Cut-off, S

BALANCE of STACKS	MATERIALS & MANUFACTURING	Water tank polyethylene	kg	5.83E-06	Polyethylene, high density, granulate {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Processing of steel to manufacture the equipments	kg	1.87E-03	Metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing {RER} processing Cut-off, S
		Processing of plastic to manufacture the water tanks	kg	5.83E-06	Extrusion of plastic sheets and thermoforming, inline {RoW} processing Cut-off, S
	EoL	Disposal (landfilling)	kg	1.87E-04	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S
		Incineration plastic water tank	kg	5.83E-06	Waste polypropylene {RoW} treatment of waste polypropylene, municipal incineration Cut-off, S
		Transportation	tkm	9.38E-04	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, euro6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S
OPERATION	UTILITIES & CONSUMABLES	Electricity	kWh	52.9	1 kWh_UBA_Electricity from wind, {GLO}, 8MW turbine, offshore Cut-off, U (of project Ibra Training)
		Feed Water (deionized)	kg	10.0	.ROB_Water, ultrapure {DE} production Cut-off, U
		KOH	kg	1.90E-03	Potassium hydroxide {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Nitrogen	kg	0.00029	Nitrogen, liquid {RER} market for Cut-off, S
		Cooling water	kg	45	.ROB_Cooling water {DE}
		Pd in deoxo catalyst (Pd/supported)	kg	6.8E-08	Palladium {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
		Al2O3 in deoxo catalyst	kg	2.3E-05	Aluminium oxide, metallurgical {IAI Area, EU27 & EFTA} market for aluminium oxide, metallurgical Cut-off, S
		Driers adsorbents	kg	1.9E-05	Zeolite, powder {GLO} market for Cut-off, S
	EoL	Disposal of Deoxocatalyst	kg	2.3E-05	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, S
		H2SO4 to neutralize lye	kg	1.7E-03	Sulfuric acid {RER} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, S
	Treatment of wastewater after lye neutralization	m3	5.7E-06	.ROB_Wastewater, COPY only for DE_average {CA-QC} treatment of wastewater, average, capacity 1.6E8l/year Cut-off, U	
ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT		Inverter	p	1.24E-06	Inverter, 500kW {RER} production Cut-off, S
		HV-MV transformer	p	9.88E-09	AEL_0a_Transformer 20 MVA (MV to LV) - updated to Ecoinvent 3.8
		MV-LV transformer	p	3.11E-08	AEL_0b_Transformer 63 MVA (HV to MV) - updated after switch to Ecoinvent 3.8

Table 7 AWE complete system: inventory and LCA mode

4.2 LCA results for the complete system

In this chapter, the LCA results for the complete system in correspondence of the three electricity scenarios will be introduced. As explained in section “product system and process units”, the so-called “*complete system*” includes all the units required to produce hydrogen, that is the “cell stack”, “electricity”, “balance of cell stack”, “operation without electricity” and “transformers and rectifier”.

In the following chapter, the focus will be on the comparison between the NEWELY AEMWE stack, and the PEMWE and AWE reference stacks. Finally, a more in depth analysis of the NEWELY AEM stack will be carried out.

4.2.1 Scenario DE grid electricity

Table 8 shows the LCA results obtained when the electrolyser is powered by German grid electricity. Figure 10 shows the same results normalized with respect to the AEM *base case*.

Hydrogen has a high impact (e.g. ~22 kgCO₂eq/kg compared to circa 10 kgCO₂eq/kg for H₂ from the standard steam methane reforming process).

AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE lead to undistinguishable environmental impact (+/-2%) because the German grid electricity dominates the LCA results (contribution >97%).

Case DE grid electricity (398 gCO ₂ eq/kWh)	Unit	AEM base case	AWE	PEM	AEM target case
GWP	(kgCO ₂ eq/kg H ₂)	21,8	21,1	22,2	21,8
Damage to human health	(DALY/kg H ₂)	2,51E-05	2,46E-05	2,54E-05	2,50E-05
Damage to ecosystem	(species.yr /kg H ₂)	9,38E-08	9,12E-08	9,53E-08	9,37E-08
Damage to resources	(USD2013/kg H ₂)	0,65	0,63	0,66	0,65
Eco-cost	(€/kg H ₂)	3,69	3,60	3,73	3,67

Table 8 LCA results: AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE complete systems – case DE grid electricity

Figure 10 LCA results: AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE complete systems – case DE grid electricity – relative results

4.2.2 Scenario southern EU PV electricity (15% availability)

As shown in Table 9, if PV electricity is applied, the impact of hydrogen decreases remarkably (e.g. from 22 kgCO₂eq/kg with German grid electricity to ~2.2 kgCO₂eq/kg).

As illustrated in Figure 11, AEM “base case” has a slightly higher impact than PEM (Δ_{\max} +14% for damage to resources). AWE leads to higher eco-cost (+20%), and damage to human health (+25%) and ecosystem (+18%).

If the lifetime of the AEM components would reach that of AWE and PEMWE (AEM *target case*), the impact of H₂ would decrease by 10-15% and become slightly lower than that of PEMWE.

Case Southern EU, PV power (34 gCO ₂ eq/kWh)	Unit	AEM base case	AWE	PEM	AEM target case
GWP	(kgCO ₂ eq/kg H ₂)	2,25	2,16	2,18	2,07
Damage to human health	(DALY/kg H ₂)	7,2E-06	9,08E-06	6,8E-06	6,5E-06
Damage to ecosystem	(species.yr /kg H ₂)	1,3E-08	1,50E-08	1,2E-08	1,2E-08
Damage to resources	(USD2013 /kg H ₂)	0,16	0,15	0,14	0,13
Eco-cost	(Euro/kg H ₂)	1,0	1,2	0,9	0,85

Table 9 LCA results: AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE complete systems – case Southern EU, PV power (15% availability)

Figure 11 LCA results: AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE complete systems – case Southern EU, PV power (15% availability) – relative results

Under those conditions, electricity remains the hot-spot. Nevertheless, the contribution of other process units, and especially of the stack, is not negligible. Note that it is practice in LCA to define cut-off criteria to limit the effort in collecting input/output data: all data contributing collectively not above the cut-off limit can be neglected. Frequently this cut-off is defined as a percentage of the total environmental impact and a 5% cut-off is often defined. According to this cut-off, the stack contribution is not negligible. Moreover, the higher impact of H₂ from the AWE system (damage to human health and ecosystem, and eco-cost) is caused by the stack.

Figure 12 LCA results for AEMWE, AWE and PEM complete systems – case PV electricity – breakdown among process units

4.2.3 Scenario DE off-shore wind electricity (50% and 98% availability)

As shown in Table 10, if German off-shore wind electricity is applied, the impact of hydrogen further decreases reaching e.g. circa 0.5 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂.

As illustrated in Figure 13, AEM *base case* has slightly higher impact than PEM (Δ_{max} +16% for damage to resources).

AWE leads to higher eco-cost (+10%), and damage to human health and ecosystem (+17%).

If the lifetime of the AEM components would reach that of AWE and PEM (AEM *target case*), the impact of H₂ would decrease by ~10-20%.

Electricity remains the hot-spot. Nevertheless, the contribution of other process units, and especially of the stack, is often above the 5% cut-off and therefore not negligible (Figure 14).

Case DE, Wind offshore power (8gCO ₂ eq/kWh)	Unit	AEM base case	AWE	PEM	AEM target case
GWP	(kgCO ₂ eq/kg H ₂)	0,57	0,54	0,54	0,51
Damage to human health	(DALY/kg H ₂)	3,14E-06	3,66E-06	3,00E-06	2,90E-06
Damage to ecosystem	(species.yr /kg H ₂)	4,16E-09	4,85E-09	4,00E-09	3,83E-09
Damage to resources	(USD2013 /kg H ₂)	0,05	0,05	0,04	0,04
Eco-cost	(Euro/kg H ₂)	0,52	0,56	0,49	0,48

Table 10 LCA results: AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE complete systems – case DE off-shore wind power (50% availability)

Figure 13 LCA results: AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE complete systems – case DE off-shore wind power (50% availability) – relative results

Figure 14 LCA results for AEMWE, AWE and PEM complete systems – case DE wind electricity 50% – breakdown among process units

Results obtained by assuming a GO/PPA scenario with German wind electricity and 98% plant availability are in Figure 15. Even in this industrially relevant case using very low impact renewable electricity, the impact of the stack might be above or close to the 5% cut-off of the total impact of electrolytic hydrogen. This is always the case for the AEM *base case* and AWE systems, no matter which LCIA methodology is selected. For PEM and AEM *target case* the contribution of the stack to the overall impact of hydrogen is around 3% (but the PEM stack contributes by 5% to the GWP of hydrogen).

Figure 15 LCA results for AEMWE, AWE and PEM complete systems – case DE wind electricity 98% – breakdown among process units

4.2.4 Effect of oxygen valorisation

As described in the paragraph “allocation”, in the present study oxygen co-produced with hydrogen was considered as vented to the atmosphere. The question was raised on the effect of valorising oxygen on the overall environmental impact. We assumed oxygen is produced in the NEWELY AEMWE system at 40 bar. According to EIGA PP33/19⁴⁸, 0.41kWh electricity is required in an air separation unit to produce high purity oxygen at 40 bar. Considering the stoichiometry of the water electrolysis reaction, for each kg of hydrogen, 8 kg of oxygen are co-produced. This would save 3.2 kWh electricity, which is circa 6% of the electricity consumed in the AEMWE

⁴⁸ https://www.eiga.eu/publications/?_sft_ct_doc_cats=position-paper

system (54.7 kWh/kg H₂). Note that this saving (6%) should not be automatically interpreted as a corresponding reduction of the environmental impact of H₂. To assess it, an allocation criterion between H₂ and O₂ should first be defined. This was beyond the scope of this study.

4.3 LCA results for the stack

As explained above, the contribution of the stack to the impact of electrolytic hydrogen is above the 5% cut-off criterion. Therefore, it is worthful to carry out a more detailed comparison of the three stacks, AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE.

4.3.1 NEWELY AEM vs PEMWE vs AWE: effect of components

Figure 16 shows the total impact of the stacks and its breakdown among their components. The diamond symbols for the PEMWE and AWE stacks show the effect of the sensitivity analyses.

The most important observations are as follows:

- The **NEWELY AEM catalyst is environmentally very advantageous** compared to the conventional AWE and PEMWE catalysts.
- The impact of the **NEWELY membrane** is higher than that of the reference systems. However this increase **does not impair the comparison between the NEWELY AEM stack and the reference stacks**.
- The remaining three major components (**PTL, BPP and stack frame**) **are the ones contributing substantially to the impact of the AEM stack**: in the *base case*, cumulatively 85% of GWP; 92%, 82% and 89% of damage to human health, ecosystem and resources, respectively; 94% of ecocost (Figure 17 left); in the *target case*, cumulatively 81% of GWP; 90%, 78% and 84% of damage to human health, ecosystem and resources, respectively; 92% of ecocost (Figure 17 right). The difference in the percentage contribution of PTL/BPP/stack frame components between the *base* and *target case* is small. This is because in these two cases the ratio of the lifetime of these three components and the other components vary only between 1.7 (=5 years/3 years) and 2 (=20 years/10 years). However in terms of absolute impact, the transition from the base to the target case has a very remarkable effect, with a decrease by a factor close to 4 of the environmental impact of the NEWELY AEM stack.
- If the **lifetime of AEM stack components** would reach that of AWE and PEM (AEM *target case*), AEM would have lower impact than PEM and much lower than AWE. Under more realistic lifetime assumptions (AEM *base case*), AEM performs in between PEM and AWE with two exceptions: GWP and damage to resources. Note that this conclusion remains valid also considering the variability of the impact results for PEMWE and AWE from the sensitivity analyses.

Figure 16 LCA results for the AEMWE, AWE and PEMWE stacks - case DE off-shore wind electricity (50% availability) - breakdown among components units

Figure 17 Contribution of AEM stack components to the stack impact. Left: *base case scenario*; right: *target case scenario*.

4.4 LCA results for the NEWELY AEM stack

In the previous paragraphs, the impact of the AEMWE stack has been compared with that of the PEMWE and AWE stacks.

In this section the attention is focused exclusively on the impact of the NEWELY AEM stack. First a contribution analysis with respect to the materials is made. Afterwards, for the most impactful stack components the contribution of their materials and the contribution of the various impact categories (for the LCA from multi-impact category methods) is investigated.

4.4.1 NEWELY AEM stack: effect of materials

Figure 18 shows the contribution of the various materials of the NEWELY AEM stack. On the right the material mass distribution is compared. Steel and PEEK are the hot-spots, with a total contribution between 67% and 90% depending on the LCIA methodology. If copper is added, the cumulative contribution reaches 90% to 95%.

It is interesting to observe that, especially for GWP and damage to resources, PEEK contributes over proportionally to the impact compared to steel and copper. This can be explained by its higher emission factor (see Figure 19 for GWP emission factors).

Figure 18 Left: Contribution of the material to the impact of the NEWELY AEM stack (base case scenario). Right: mass distribution of the materials in the NEWELY AEM stack.

Figure 19 GWP emissions factor for the major materials of the AEM NEWELY stack

4.4.2 NEWELY AEM stack components: activities and impact categories

Figure 20 shows the breakdown of the GWP of the AEM NEWELY stack into its components. Moreover, for the more impactful components, i.e. PTL, BPP and stack frame, the breakdown into materials/activities is shown.

Analogous figures for the other LCIA methods (ReCiPe Endpoints and eco-cost) are shown below (Figure 21 to Figure 24). As those are multi-impact category methods, in the main pictures the breakdown into the impact categories is also given.

The most important take-aways are:

- The impact of the PTL is dominated by stainless steel, no matter which LCIA among the selected ones is applied.
- The impact of the BPP is dominated by PEEK
- Steel and copper dominate the impact of the stack frame
- According to both ReCiPe and eco-cost methodology, GWP is not sufficient to properly describe the overall impact of the AEM stack.

Figure 20 GWP impact of the AEM NEWELY stack, with breakdown into components and materials.

Figure 21 ReCiPe damage to human health for the AEM NEWELY stack, with breakdown into impact categories, components, and materials.

ReCiPe Endpoints H: Damage to ecosystem

MAJOR CONTRIBUTORS:

Impact categories:

Global warm., terr eco	48%
Acidification	25%
Ecotoxicity	7%
Others	20%

Components:

STACK FRAME	35%
BPP	26%
PTL/MPL	21%
Membrane	11%
Others	7%

Materials:

STEEL	39%
Cu	26%
PEEK	28%
Ni	4%
Others	3%

Figure 22 ReCiPe damage to the ecosystem for the AEM NEWELY stack, with breakdown into impact categories, components, and materials.

ReCiPe Endpoints H: Damage to Resources

MAJOR CONTRIBUTORS:

Impact categories:

Fossil res. scarcity	85%
Mineral res. scarcity	15%

Components:

BPP	55%
STACK FRAME	18%
PTL/MPL	15%
Others	12%

Materials:

PEEK	62%
STEEL	28%
Cu	6%
Ni	1%
Other	3%

Figure 23 ReCiPe damage to resources for the AEM NEWELY stack, with breakdown into impact categories, components, and materials.

Figure 24 Eco-cost impact of the AEM NEWELY stack, with breakdown into impact categories, components, and materials.

5 Conclusions

- The present LCA study shows that, even with renewable electricity, **electricity dominates the environmental impact of electrolytic hydrogen**. This conclusion remains valid independently of the selected water electrolysis technology (NEWELY AEM or reference PEMWE and AWE) and of the selected LCIA methodology (IPCC 2021 GWP100y, ReCiPe 2016 Endpoints H, Eco-cost 2017). Therefore, electricity consumption and electricity sourcing are the most important levers to decrease the environmental impact of hydrogen from electrolysis.
- Nevertheless, even with the best renewable electricity (i.e. renewable electricity with low environmental impact such as German wind off-shore power) and assuming 98% plant availability (i.e. GO/PPA configuration) the **other activities beyond electricity consumption are not negligible for a comprehensive quantification of the environmental impact of electrolytic hydrogen**. In fact, the cumulative contribution of all the other activities (cell stack, balance of stack, electrical equipment, operation without electricity) is above the 5% cut-off generally applied in LCA. This contribution varies depending on the stack type (NEWELY AEM, AWE, PEMWE) and LCIA methodology: 15%+/-5% for NEWELY AEM (*base case*), 17%+/-3% for AWE, 8%+/-2% for PEMWE. Among those activities, the stack contributes the most. We conclude that:
 - from an LCA point of view, a complete life cycle inventory is required for a comprehensive assessment of the environmental impact of hydrogen, and
 - **the stack is the second contributor after electricity**.
- **The relative environmental impact of the NEWELY AEM stack compared to the AWE and PEMWE references is affected by the still unknown lifetime of its components**. To cope with this uncertainty two cases were assessed throughout the study: the “*target case*” where AEM components are assumed to reach, in the future, the lifetime of the corresponding AWE and PEMWE components, and the “*base case*” where the lifetime of the AEM components is three or four times shorter than that of AWE and PEMWE.

Under the *target case* the NEWELY AEM stack performs environmentally better than PEMWE and much better than AWE. This conclusion remains valid even considering the uncertainty related to the PEM and AWE system and related to the emission factors for Pt and Ir, and Ni, respectively. However, under the presently more realistic *base case* assumptions, the AEM system performs in between PEM and AWE, with the exception of GWP and ReCiPe damage to resources. For these impacts, the AEM stack performs worse than AWE and especially PEMWE stacks.

- **The AEM NEWELY catalyst is definitely environmentally beneficial compared to conventional PEM** (supported Pt and Ir) and AWE (Ni-based). The impact of the NEWELY membrane is higher than that of the reference systems. However, its contribution to the overall impact is modest. Therefore this increase does not negatively impair the comparison of the NEWELY AEM stack with the reference stacks.
- On the other site, the remaining three main stack components of the AEM NEWELY stack (**stack frame, BPP and PTL**) are the ones dominating the impact, with a cumulative contribution between 80% and 90% depending on the selected LCIA methodology. The high impact of those components overcompensates the benefit associated with the more

environmentally friendly catalyst of the AEMWE NEWELY stack. It is especially the high impact of the PEEK used for the BPP that leads to the higher GWP and higher ReCiPe damage to resources. Note that more **sustainable PEEK** materials have been developed by Evonik (Vestamin® RFP = reduced footprint)⁴⁹, who claims a reduction of the C-footprint by 40% and of water consumption and land use change by 99%. This could potentially be a low hanging fruit to reduce the environmental impact of the NEWELY BPP without forgoing the excellent mechanical and chemical resistance properties of PEEK at high temperatures. For the other two high impact components, the stack frame and PTL, **stainless steel and copper** are at the origin of the environmental impact. Their **substitution with recycled metals** (100% recyclability of both materials possible) could strongly reduce the impact.

- According to the two multi-impact LCIA methodologies selected for this study, ReCiPe endpoints and Eco-cost, global warming potential alone is not sufficient to quantify the total impact of the stack.

The major **limitation** of this study is the current **absence of a long-term performance test** of the NEWELY stack, which will be realized at the end of the project. Moreover, at the time this report was written, the **development of the NEWELY cell design was still in progress**. Thus, this investigation assesses the impact of a not yet fully optimized NEWELY system.

⁴⁹ <https://www.vestamid.com/de/verbesserter-fussabdruck-von-polyamid-12-vestamid-durch-nachhaltige-energie-163680.html>